

The Effect of Job Stress and Job Satisfaction on Organizational Commitment Mediated by Work Life Balance

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze whether the influence of job stress and job satisfaction on organizational commitment mediated by work-life balance on employees at PT Pos Indonesia. The population consists of all Pos Indonesia employees at the Solo, Sukoharjo, and Sragen branch offices. By using simple random sampling technique, the number of respondents obtained was 215 to 430 respondents. Validity and reliability tests were used in this study, model suitability using the goodness of fit test and the t-test to test the hypothesis. Data analysis used Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis and the software used was Smart PLS. The results of the study showed that job satisfaction had a significant effect on work-life balance, job stress had a significant effect on work-life balance, and work-life balance had a significant effect on organizational commitment. Then for the mediation role, the results showed that job satisfaction had an effect on organizational commitment moderated by work-life balance and work stress had an effect on organizational commitment moderated by work-life balance.

KEYWORDS: Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Work Life Balance, Work Stress

INTRODUCTION

In today's fast-paced and highly competitive work environment, achieving work-life balance has become a significant concern for employees and organizations. Work-life balance (WLB) is defined as the degree to which an individual achieves a balance between their roles and responsibilities at work and outside of work, without one interfering with the other (Kelliher et al., 2019). However, achieving this balance can be difficult due to factors such as job stress and job satisfaction that can significantly impact an individual's ability to manage their work and personal lives (Aruldos et al., 2021).

Job stress is one of the main factors that can negatively affect work-life balance. High levels of job stress can lead to physical and emotional exhaustion, which can make it difficult for employees to find time and energy for their personal lives (Wood et al., 2020). In contrast, job satisfaction and job commitment are positively related to work-life balance, as they can lead to greater job autonomy, flexibility, and work-life integration (Bellmann & Hübler, 2021).

Research has shown that work-life balance has significant implications for organizational commitment. Work-life balance practices can have a positive impact on organizational commitment, which refers to employees' psychological attachment and loyalty to their organization (Oyewobi et al., 2019). When employees perceive that their work and personal lives are balanced, they are more likely to be satisfied with their jobs and committed to their organizations. This is because work-life balance practices can signal to employees that their employers value their well-being, which in turn fosters feelings of trust, loyalty, and commitment (Taluđer, 2019).

Additionally, employees who feel they have achieved work-life balance are less likely to experience burnout and quit intentions, which can result in a more stable and engaged workforce. This, in turn, can lead to better organizational performance, as engaged employees are more likely to be engaged, productive, and willing to go above and beyond their job requirements (Jaharuddin & Zainol, 2019). Therefore, it is important for organizations to recognize the importance of work-life balance practices not only for employee well-being but also for organizational commitment and performance. By implementing strategies to reduce work stress and increase job satisfaction and job commitment, organizations can create a positive work environment that fosters organizational commitment and ultimately leads to better organizational outcomes (Wolor et al., 2020).

Spillover theory explains that there is a mutual influence of personal life on work and vice versa. This is the basis for thinking that work-life balance can act as a mediator of work stress and job satisfaction on organizational commitment. Work stress, which is one of the main problems in modern organizations, will be a negative effect of work that will affect personal life. From the personal life problems that arise, it can disrupt the work-life balance which will then make someone uncomfortable at work (Skakon et al,

2010). Given the importance of these factors, it is very important to investigate the relationship between work stress, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment, and how work-life balance can act as a mediating variable. The role of mediating variables in research is to further understand the process or mechanism of variables to provide effects. Mediating variables are used to try to identify the process that bridges the independent variable with the dependent variable. With research involving mediating variables, it is hoped that a new prediction model will emerge that increases accuracy and clarifies the relationship between independent and dependent variables (Collins et al, 1998).

This aims to explore the relationship between these variables and provide insights into how organizations can promote work-life balance to enhance organizational commitment. This thesis is compiled by combining two previous research models, namely (Aruldoss et al., 2021) which discusses the relationship between quality of work life (QWL) and work-life balance (WLB) with job stress, job satisfaction, and job commitment as mediators in transportation sector workers in India and (Oyewobi et al., 2019) which investigates the relationship between work-life balance (WLB) and organizational performance with organizational commitment as a mediator in construction workers in Nigeria. From the research of Aruldoss et al (2020) the researcher took the relationship between job stress and job satisfaction with work-life balance and then combined it with the research model of Oyewobi et al (2019) which has a model of the relationship between work-life balance (WLB) and organizational commitment. In addition, the researcher tried to use other types of business sectors, namely the postal, courier, and logistics services sectors which are different from the two previous studies. The postal, courier, and logistics services sector was chosen as the research object theme due to the increasing need for courier and logistics services along with the massive development of technology that makes it easier for people to make online purchases. Pos Indonesia, which initially only focused on money letter delivery services, has now made several product innovations such as package delivery services in order to serve the needs of the community in online shopping or delivery of goods to be able to compete with newly formed delivery service companies (Oktabriyanti et al., 2021). Based on internal data from the Solo Post Office throughout 2021, deliveries never reached 100% of the standard delivery time, with the average percentage of packages successfully delivered within the standard delivery time still at 81.2%. With these problems still existing, if they are not resolved immediately, it will have an impact on the loss of consumers who switch to other delivery service providers. Moreover, currently there are many delivery service providers in the form of start-ups that have received capital injections from venture capital, making competition in this sector even higher. With such high competition, the operational error rate is required to always be zero, because delivery errors and delays are very fatal and will worsen the company's image, this demand also has the potential to cause work stress.

Seeing this, Pos Indonesia is considered interesting to be used as a research object because Pos Indonesia has stood strong since its inception amidst the onslaught of other delivery service providers. This can be maintained by continuing to create a comfortable working environment for its workers (Pratama, 2020). In addition, researchers want to know the things that influence the formation of organizational commitment in Pos Indonesia so that it can later be a reference if a company wants to foster a sense of organizational commitment in its employees.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a person's positive feelings about his/her job, including satisfaction with salary, work environment, coworkers, company policies, and career development opportunities (Locke, 1969). Job satisfaction also involves a person's perception of the fit between his/her abilities and interests and the demands of the job, as well as satisfaction with the results obtained from his/her work. The higher a person's level of job satisfaction, the less likely they are to experience work stress, absenteeism, or quit their job (Zhu, 2013).

Work Stress and Work-life Balance

The Work-life balance Spillover theory states that a person's attitudes, emotions, behaviors, and abilities that appear in one domain, be it work or personal life, will flow into another domain (Balmforth & Gardner, 2006; Frone, 2003; Zedeck, 1992). This shows that personal life and work conditions will influence each other. Spillover can have positive or negative effects, and can occur in both directions - from work to personal life and from personal life to work (Balmforth & Gardner, 2006; Hanson, et al., 2006; Hill, et al., 2001). This can be interpreted that if the work environment is toxic, which makes employees' emotions worse, then over time it will also have a negative effect on personal life, and vice versa.

H1: Work stress has a negative effect on work-life balance.

2. Job Stress

Job stress is a condition of imbalance between work demands and a person's ability to deal with those demands (Hassard et al., 2018).

Job Satisfaction and Work-life Balance

Social exchange theory states that a person's behavior is influenced by their expectation of rewards. In the work context, this means that employees tend to be more satisfied with their jobs if they believe they are treated fairly and are fairly rewarded for their contributions. As a result of this sense of satisfaction, they are more likely to be able to set boundaries between their work and personal lives. They are also more likely to take breaks when they need them and not let their work stress them out. On the other hand, employees who are dissatisfied with their jobs are more likely to experience work-life imbalance. They may feel like they are always working and never have time for themselves or their families. They are also more likely to experience stress and burnout.

H2: Job Satisfaction has a positive effect on Work-life balance

3. Work-life balance

Work-life balance is a condition in which a person has a balance of time, energy, and attention between work and personal life. This means that a person can balance the demands of work and their personal and family needs. This includes prioritizing time to rest, socialize, develop hobbies, and maintain physical and mental health. A balance between work and personal life can help improve a person's well-being, performance, and productivity in the workplace (Lockwood, 2003).

Work-life balance and Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment refers to the level of attachment, loyalty, and involvement of employees to the organization where they work. Meyer et al. (1991) suggested that there are three elements of organizational commitment: affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. Affective commitment describes the emotional attachment of employees to their organization. Continuance commitment explains employees' perceptions of the potential risks and impacts associated with leaving their current organization. While normative commitment describes the state in which employees want to remain in the organization because they feel they have an obligation and responsibility to the organization that employs them for certain reasons. High organizational commitment in employees will of course be very beneficial to the company because it will be able to reduce turnover and strengthen employee performance.

H3: Work-life balance has a positive effect on Organizational commitment

4. Organizational commitment

Organizational commitment can be interpreted as an individual's attitude towards the organization where he works, which is reflected in the level of his willingness to maintain his membership in the organization (Mowday, 1998).

Work-life balance as a Mediator

The role of mediating variables in research is to further understand the process or mechanism of variables to provide effects. Mediating variables are used to try to identify the process that bridges the independent variable with the dependent variable. In this study, WLB is used as a mediator with the aim of analyzing whether WLB can provide an effect to further explain and strengthen the effect of the relationship between work stress and job satisfaction on organizational commitment. With research involving mediating variables, it is hoped that a new prediction model will emerge that increases accuracy and clarifies the relationship between independent and dependent variables (Collins et al, 1998).

H4: Job Stress has a positive effect on Organizational commitment mediated by Work life balance

H5: Job Satisfaction has a positive effect on Organizational commitment mediated by Work life balance

DATA AND METHODS

Research design is a plan and strategy used to collect data and answer the problem formulation in a systematic and scientific manner. Research design is useful as a clear and structured framework for collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data. In general, this study has a problem formulation "do job stress and job satisfaction affect Organizational commitment with Work life balance

as a mediating variable?". This study uses a quantitative approach, which means that the research is carried out with a formal, objective, systematic process, and uses numerical data to interpret the phenomena that occur (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). To collect data, a survey method is used in the form of a questionnaire. The use of surveys is carried out because the data used is data from the results of respondents' opinions on the question items in the questionnaire. Then the data obtained from the questionnaire will be processed and analyzed to test the hypotheses that have been prepared. This study is a cross-sectional study, which means that the data is taken at a certain point in time.

The population consists of all Pos Indonesia employees at the Solo, Sukoharjo, and Sragen branch offices. By using simple random sampling technique, the number of respondents obtained was 215 to 430 respondents.

Sampling techniques in research refer to the methods or procedures used to select samples from a larger population. The right sampling technique is essential to ensure the validity and generalizability of research results. In this study, a simple random sampling technique was used, which means that every element in the population has an equal chance of being selected as part of the sample.

This study used a questionnaire with a rating scale system, namely using a Likert scale of 1-5, with a scale of 1 meaning strongly disagree, a scale of 2 meaning disagree, a scale of 3 meaning neutral, a scale of 4 meaning agree, and a scale of 5 meaning strongly agree.

1. Independent Variable

The independent variable is a variable in a study that is a cause or factor that will affect the dependent variable. In a study, this variable is often symbolized by X, and has another name, the predictor variable. In this study, there are three independent variables, namely:

a. Job Satisfaction

In measuring the job satisfaction variable, the researcher used 12 items by adapting the question indicators in the research by Aruldoss et al (2020) as follows:

- 1) I am satisfied with the responsibilities given to me for my work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 2) I feel happy with my work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 3) I get recognition in my work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 4) I feel like I have achieved something in my work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 5) I get a fair promotion at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 6) I am satisfied with my family life with me working at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 7) I am happy with the job security provided by the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 8) I feel like I am developing while working at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 9) I am satisfied with the working conditions at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 10) I am satisfied with the salary given by the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 11) I can feel the cooperation between me and the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 12) I am satisfied with the communication pattern between me and my superiors at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City

b. Job Stress

In measuring the job stress variable, the researcher used 9 items by adapting the question indicators in the research of Shukla and Srivastava (2016) and Aruldoss et al (2020) as follows:

1. I experience physical and mental health problems related to work at the Solo City Post Office
2. I experience noise pollution that interferes with the smooth running of work at the Solo City Post Office
3. Office conditions such as tables, chairs, bathrooms, etc. at the Solo City Post Office are in poor condition
4. The condition of work equipment such as computers, machines, office vehicles at the Solo City Post Office often jam or have problems when operating
5. There are often too many customers at the Solo City Post Office
6. There are often problems with the work process at the Solo City Post Office
7. The work flow system at the Solo City Post Office makes me stressed

8. The Solo City Post Office will not take action against me if there are complaints or demands from customers that are not caused by my fault

9. The amount of compensation I receive at the Solo City Post Office creates anxiety for me

2. Variables Mediation

A mediating variable is a variable that functions as a link between two other variables. The mediating variable will affect the relationship between the variables that are directly related. In this study, the mediating variable is Work life balance.

a. Work life balance

In measuring the Work life balance variable, researchers used 10 items by adapting the question indicators used by Aruldoss et al (2020) and Oyewobi (2019) as follows:

- 1) I have enough time to spend with my family even though I work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 2) I have enough time to take care of my children even though I work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 3) I have enough time to take care of elderly family members who depend on me even though I work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 4) I don't miss important social events even though I work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 5) I have enough time to have a health check-up even though I work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 6) I can manage work responsibilities and personal aspirations (eg personal life goals, family planning) effectively.
- 7) I have a focus outside myself that brings me peace (e.g. hobbies, spiritual activities, and community development.).
- 8) When I am at home, I am free from worries about work matters.
- 9) When I am at work, I am free from worries about personal matters.
- 10) I am satisfied with my life outside of work.

3. Dependent Variable

A dependent variable is a variable whose value depends on another variable in a study. In a study, the dependent variable is the variable that is measured to see if there is an influence or change that occurs due to changes in the independent variable. Often the dependent variable is symbolized by the letter Y. In this study, the dependent variable is Organizational commitment.

a. Organizational commitment

In measuring the Organizational commitment variable, researchers used 8 items by adapting the question indicators first formulated by Allen and Meyer (1990) which are still adapted today as in Malone and Issa (2013), and Grego-Planer (2014) as follows:

- 1) I feel like I am part of the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 2) The Indonesian Post Office in Solo City is able to inspire me to bring out my best potential in terms of performance
- 3) I really care about the fate of ...
- 4) I never want to leave my job at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City forever
- 5) I am proud to tell others that I am part of the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 6) There are many things that can be obtained by staying with the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City for an unlimited time
- 7) I cannot work for another organization even though I have the same type of work
- 8) I feel that there is a very significant change in my life if I leave the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 9) I feel that my values and the values of the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City are very similar
- 10) I am willing to accept almost all types of tasks job to continue working at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City
- 11) I am willing to put in a lot of effort, beyond what is usually expected, to help the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City become more developed
- 12) The Indonesian Post Office in Solo City deserves my loyalty

Instrument Test

In this study, respondents' sincerity is required in answering the statements in the questionnaire. For this reason, instrument testing is needed, namely validity testing and reliability testing. Validity testing is used to test whether the indicator is able to measure the measured variable, it is said to be valid if the statement in the questionnaire can reveal something that will be measured by the

questionnaire. While the reliability test is related to the consistency of the answers to each indicator. Testing the validity and reliability of the instrument in this study will use Smart PLS.

1. Validity Test

The validity test is a test carried out to determine whether the indicator used can measure the variable being studied (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The analysis method used for the validity test in this study is confirmatory factor analysis by looking at the loading factor value. In this study, the sample used was around 250 respondents, therefore the indicator can be declared valid if the loading factor value is ≥ 0.35 (Hair et al, 2019).

2. Reliability Test

Reliability Test is a test to ensure that the measuring instrument used in this study is consistent and accurate. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2016) the type of reliability used during the study is the internal consistency reliability method which includes the extent to which the instrument items have homogeneous properties and provide the same underlying construct. The decision to test this reliability is if Cronbach's Alpha ≥ 0.60 then the statement item is declared reliable (Sekaran, 2016).

Data Analysis

The data analysis method used in this study is to obtain descriptive statistics of respondents and test the six hypotheses in this study, namely using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis tool and the software used is Smart PLS.

Data Testing

Before conducting a hypothesis test, it is best to conduct a model suitability test or goodness of fit test.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is conducted to determine the influence between independent variables on the dependent variable (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016b). Hypothesis testing is conducted on the basis of decision making, namely by comparing the magnitude of the p value with a level of significance of 5% (alpha 0.05).

DISCUSSIONS

A. Statistik Deskriptif

Descriptive statistics aim to describe and provide an overview of variables indicated by mean and standard deviation values. The mean value indicates the average value of the assessment of all respondents' answers to the variables studied, while the standard deviation indicates the diversity of respondents' answers (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). If the standard deviation value given is close to zero, the respondents' answers will be less varied, but if the standard deviation given is far from zero, the respondents' answers will be more varied.

1. Respondent Characteristics

Respondent characteristics are known from the recapitulation of questionnaire answers that have been distributed to 230 respondents.

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

Profile		Frequency	Presentation (%)
Gender	Man	143	62%
	Woman	87	38%
Age	< 30 year	55	24%
	30 – 39 year	104	45%
	40 – 50 year	48	21%
	> 50 year	23	10%
Education	SMA/SMK	147	64%
	Diploma/Bachelor	83	36%
Office	Surakarta City	64	28%
	Laweyan	14	6%
	Serengan	16	7%

	Kliwon Market	18	8%
	Jebres	19	8%
	Banjarsari	20	9%
	Sukoharjo	24	10%
	Sragen	55	24%
Working Age	< 1 year	48	21%
	1 – 3 year	44	19%
	3 – 6 year	113	49%
	6 – 10 year	19	8%
	> 10 year	6	3%

Based on the respondent data above, it can be seen that the majority of respondents in this study were male, totaling 143 people or 62%. Based on the age of the respondents, the majority were aged 30 to 39 years, totaling 104 people or 45%. Based on education level, the majority of respondents were high school/vocational high school graduates, totaling 147 people or 64%. Based on the respondents' job placement offices, the most were located in Surakarta and Sragen, 28% and 28% respectively, this is because the two post offices are the largest in the Solo City area. Based on working age, the majority of respondents have worked at the Post Office for 3-6 years, totaling 113 people or 49%.

2. Respondent responses

Respondent responses presented in descriptive statistics aim to describe and provide an overview of the variables indicated by the mean and standard deviation values. The mean value indicates the average value of the assessment of all respondents' answers to the variables studied, while the standard deviation indicates the diversity of respondents' answers (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). If the standard deviation value given is close to zero, the respondents' answers will be less varied, but if the standard deviation given is far from zero, the respondents' answers will be more varied.

a. Job Satisfaction

The results of the descriptive statistical calculations for the Job Satisfaction variable can be seen in table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of job satisfaction

Question Items	Mean	Std. dev
I am satisfied with the responsibilities given to me for work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City.	4.07	0.70
I feel happy with my job at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City	4.08	0.64
I got recognition in my work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City	3.96	0.72
I feel like I have achieved something in my work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City	3.91	0.76
Saya mendapatkan promosi yang adil di Kantor Pos Indonesia Kota Solo	3.56	0.85
I got a fair promotion at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City	3.92	0.73
I am happy with the job security provided by the Indonesian Post Office of Solo City	3.93	0.66
I feel like I'm growing while working at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City	3.82	0.75
I am satisfied with the working conditions at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City	3.93	0.66

I am satisfied with the salary given by the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City	3.62	0.81
I can feel the cooperation between me and the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City	3.90	0.67
I am satisfied with the communication pattern between me and my superiors at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City.	3.86	0.81
Average	3.88	0.73

Based on table 2 descriptive statistics can be seen for the variable Job Satisfaction measured using 12 statement items and obtained an average value of 3.88 which means that the respondents' answers tend to be more towards a sense of satisfaction when working at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City. The standard deviation value for the Job Satisfaction variable is 0.73 which shows that the respondents' answers are quite close to the average value, this indicates low variance, and the respondents' answers are consistent.

b. Job Stres

The results of the descriptive statistical calculations for the Work Stress variable can be seen in table 3.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics Job Stress

Question Items	Mean	Std. dev
I have health problems both physically and mentally related to work at the Solo City Post Office.	2.22	1.13
I experienced noise pollution that disrupted the smooth running of work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City.	2.28	1.03
The condition of the office such as tables, chairs, bathrooms, etc. at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City are in poor condition.	2.74	1.19
The condition of work equipment such as computers, machines, office vehicles at the Solo City Indonesian Post Office often jams or has problems when operating.	2.76	1.07
There are often too many customers at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City	3.05	0.95
There are frequent disruptions to the work process at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City	2.74	1.05
The work flow system at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City makes me stressed	2.33	1.03
The Solo City Indonesian Post Office will not take action against me if there is a customer complaint or claim that was not caused by my fault	2.73	1.10
The amount of compensation I received at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City created a sense of anxiety for me.	2.64	1.02
Average	2.61	1.06

Based on table 3, descriptive statistics can be seen for the Work Stress variable measured using 9 statement items and obtained an average value of 2.61 which means that the respondents' answers tend to not feel work stress when working at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City. The standard deviation value for the Work Stress variable is 1.06 which shows that the respondents' answers have a high variance.

c. Worklife Balance

The results of the descriptive statistical calculations for the Work-life balance variable can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics Work Life Balance

Question Items	Mean	Std. dev
I have enough time to spend with my family even though I work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City.	3.39	0.96
I have enough time to take care of my children even though I work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City.	3.48	0.90
I have enough time to take care of elderly family members who depend on me even though I work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City.	3.51	0.78
I don't miss important social events even though I work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City.	3.44	0.86
I have enough time to do a health check even though I work at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City	3.64	0.80
I can manage work responsibilities and personal aspirations (e.g. personal life goals, family planning) effectively.	3.71	0.71
I have an area of focus outside of myself that brings me peace (e.g. hobbies, spiritual pursuits, community development, etc.).	3.64	0.72
When I am at home, I am free from worries about work matters.	3.26	0.94
When I am at work, I am free from worries about everyday personal affairs.	3.27	0.81
I feel satisfied with my life outside of work.	3.66	0.72
Average	3.50	0.82

Based on table 4, descriptive statistics can be seen for the Worklife Balance variable measured using 9 statement items and obtained an average value of 3.50 which means that respondents' answers tend to feel that their Worklife Balance is well maintained when working at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City. The standard deviation value for the Worklife Balance variable is 0.82 which shows that respondents' answers are quite close to the average value, this indicates low variance, and respondents' answers are consistent.

d. Organizational commitment

The results of the descriptive statistical calculations for the Organizational Commitment variable can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics Organization Commitment

Question Items	Mean	Std. dev
I feel like I am part of the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City	4.04	0.74
The Indonesian Post Office in Solo City was able to inspire me to bring out my best potential in terms of performance.	3.78	0.81
I really care about fate organization	3.95	0.78
I never wanted to leave my job at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City forever.	3.72	0.86
I never wanted to leave my job at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City forever.	3.99	0.80

There are many things that can be obtained by staying with the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City for an unlimited time.	3.81	0.80
I cannot work for another organization even though it has the same type of work.	3.39	0.90
I feel that there will be a very significant change in my life if I leave the Solo City Indonesian Post Office.	3.44	0.79
I feel that my values and the values of the Indonesian Post Office of Solo City are very similar.	3.57	0.76
I am willing to accept almost any type of job assignment to continue working at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City	3.60	0.83
I am willing to put in a lot of effort, beyond what is usually expected, to help the Indonesian Post Office of Solo City to become more developed.	3.74	0.80
The Indonesian Post Office of Solo City deserves my loyalty	3.79	0.75
Average	3.74	0.80

Based on table 5 descriptive statistics can be seen for the variable Organizational Commitment measured using 12 statement items and obtained an average value of 3.74 which means that the respondents' answers lead to good Organizational Commitment while working at the Indonesian Post Office in Solo City. The standard deviation value for the Organizational Commitment variable is 0.80 which shows that the respondents' answers are quite close to the average value, this indicates low variance, and the respondents' answers are consistent.

B. Model Test

1. Outer Model

Data analysis using the structural equation analysis method or can be called the Structural Equation Model (SEM) which is completed with the Partial Least Square (PLS) program which is used as a general method in providing estimates on the path model using latent constructs from a number of indicators. The tests that will be carried out are:

a. Convergen validity

The first step is testing the validity of the question items, using convergent validity which can be seen from the outer loading value. A question item can be said to be valid if it has an outer loading value ≥ 0.7 and has been perfectly extracted (Hair et al., 2014). The results of the convergent validity test of this study are presented in Appendix validity test.

The results of the convergent validity test which can be seen in appendix validity test, explain that all question items in this research questionnaire were perfectly extracted and had an outer loading of more than 0.7. This criterion is in accordance with Hair et al., (2019) that data is declared valid if the value is > 0.7 . This proves that all question items can explain the research construct perfectly and have an outer loading ≥ 0.7 , this proves that all question items can explain the research construct well.

b. Discriminant validity

The next test is to see the cross loading factor value or can be called a discriminant validity test. This test is carried out to see whether the reflective constructs have a strong relationship with each indicator. This test is carried out by comparing the construct values with each other. The following can be seen the cross loading value in appendix table 1.

In appendix table 1, it can be seen that there are differences in cross loading values for each variable between indicators or question items. Thus, the discriminant validity test in this study did not find any problems.

c. Average Variance Extracted

The next validity test is to look at the Average Variance Extracted or AVE. Values that have a magnitude of more than 0.5 are the values expected to appear in this AVE test. Table 6 presents the AVE values of all variables in the study.

Table 6. Calculation Results Average Variance Extracted

Variabel	AVE
Job Satisfaction	0,572
Job Stress	0,514
<i>Worklife Balance</i>	0,576
<i>Organizational Behaviour</i>	0,584

In table 6 above, it can be seen that there are variables in the study that have an AVE value of more than 0.5 so that it can be said to be valid. The product brand variable is the variable with the highest AVE, which is 0.828. In the convergent validity test, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value is also required. According to Hair et al., (2014), the AVE value that can be accepted for convergent validity is > 0.5 . The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value for all question items in this study has met the minimum criteria, which is greater than > 0.5 . This can be interpreted as a validity test for convergent based on outer loading and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value has been met, because the average variance value explained by each indicator in each construct tested is greater than the error value in the construct, so that all existing indicators can explain the construct compared to other factors that are not measured in the measurement (Hair et al., 2014).

d. Cronbach Alpha

Cronbach's alpha testing is to see the reliability of research items. The test results can be said to have a high level of reliability with consistency if they are getting closer to one. Cronbach's alpha can be accepted or said to be reliable if it has a value of more than 0.7. The following table 7 shows the results of the reliability of the research variables.

Table 7. Calculation Results Cronbach's Alpha

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha
Job Satisfaction	0,931
Job Stress	0,880
<i>Worklife Balance</i>	0,920
<i>Organizational commitment</i>	0,926

Based on the results of the Cronbach's alpha test shown in Table 7, it can be interpreted that all variables in this study are reliable because they have met the requirements of a Cronbach's alpha value of more than 0.7.

e. Composite reability

The next reliability test is to look at the composite reliability value. This is used to find out whether the variable can be said to be reliable or not. Research indicators can be said to be reliable if repeated measurements will produce consistent results (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Similar to Cronbach's alpha, the composite reliability value can be said to be reliable if it has a value of more than 0.7. The following table 8 shows the results of the composite reliability of the research variables.

Table 8. Calculation Results Composite Realibility

Variabel	Composite realibility
Job Satisfaction	0,936
Job Stress	0,917
<i>Worklife Balance</i>	0,926
<i>Organizational commitment</i>	0,940

In table 8 above, it can be seen that each variable in this study has a composite reliability value greater than 0.7. Thus, it can be concluded that each variable has passed the reliability test.

2. *Struktural model evaluation*

Hypothesis testing using the (PLS-SEM) method is important to understand that adjusting the model to the sample data to be able to get the best parameter prediction by maximizing the explained variance of the endogenous latent variables (Hair et al, 2014). There are several steps in the structural equation model that must be done, including:

a. *Testing the Coefficient of Determination (R-Square)*

In using PLS-SEM analysis, researchers must be careful in interpreting and using the fit model (Hair et al., 2014). The value of the R-Square test results can be interpreted as the influence of exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables. The higher the R-Square value, the better the prediction model of the proposed research model. The coefficient is a measure of the accuracy of the model's prediction and is calculated as the squared correlation between the original value and the estimated value of a particular endogenous variable (Hair et al., 2014). The results of the coefficient of determination in this study are shown in table 9.

Table 9. Calculation Results Koefisien Determinasi

Variabel	R-square
Worklife Balance	0,365
Organizational commitment	0,521

It can be seen from table 9 above shows the results of the coefficient of determination in the study. The value of the Organizational Commitment variable is 0.521 or equal to 52.1% which means that job satisfaction, job stress, and Worklife Balance have a moderate influence to explain the variance of intention to apply for a job. Therefore, the remaining 47.9% is explained by other variables that are not in the study. Furthermore, the Worklife Balance variable has a value of 0.365 or equal to 36.5% which means that job satisfaction and work stress have a moderate influence to explain Worklife Balance.

b. *Effect size (F Square)*

The next test is to see the value of the change that will occur in R-Square when the exogenous variable is removed from the model. The measurement standards used are 0.02 for weak, 0.15 for moderate, and 0.35 for large. The results of the F Square value in this study are shown in table 10.

Table 10. Calculation Results Effect size

	Job satisfaction	Job Stress	Worklife Balance	Organizational commitment
Job satisfaction			0,334	0,518
Job Stress			0,049	0,002
Worklife Balance				0,036

Based on table 10, it can be seen that the effect size of the Job Satisfaction variable to Worklife Balance is 0.334, so it has a strong influence. For Job Stress to Worklife Balance has an effect size of 0.049, meaning it has a weak influence. Furthermore, Worklife Balance on Organizational commitment has an effect size of 0.036, which means it has a weak influence.

C. *Uji Hypothesis*

Hypothesis testing will be tested using Partial Least Square especially on variables with reflective and formative indicators. After the GoF criteria are met for the prediction of the structural model, a new hypothesis analysis can be carried out. In the first hypothesis, a test of the level of significance of the relationship between variables in the model is carried out based on the CR value compared to the Z table. In general, studies use a significance P value of 5%. If the results of the test do not meet the significance requirements, it can be interpreted that the hypothesis is not supported. The results of the hypothesis testing are presented in the following figure and table:

Table 11. Calculation Results Direct Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis	Estimates	T statistics	P-Value
Job Satisfaction with WLB	0,499	9,640	0,000
Job Stress with WLB	-0,183	2,805	0.006
WLB with OC	0,148	2,420	0,028
Job Satisfaction with OC	0,606	14,04	0,000
Job Stress with OC	0,002	0,054	0.561

Table 12. Calculation Results Indirect Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis	Estimates	T statistics	P-Value
Job Satisfaction with WLB on <i>Organizational commitment</i>	0,074	2,356	0,019
Job Stress with WLB on <i>Organizational commitment</i>	-0,027	1,714	0.087

Figure 1 Model Penelitian pada Smart PLS

Based on tables 11 and 12 above, the results of the hypothesis testing can be said to be significant or influential with a confidence level of 5% ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$) (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The positive original sample value indicates that the hypothesis has a positive influence and vice versa. Based on the image and table above, it can be concluded regarding the hypothesis as follows:

1. *Hypothesis 1*

Ho1 : Job Satisfaction does not have a positive effect on Work Life Balance

Ha1 : Job Satisfaction has a positive effect on Work Life Balance

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, the p-value is $0.000 \leq 0.05$ (error rate $\alpha = 5\%$) so Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. This means that Job Satisfaction has a positive effect on Worklife Balance. This means that if Job Satisfaction increases, Worklife Balance will also increase and vice versa, if Job Satisfaction decreases, Worklife Balance will also decrease. The estimate value of 0.499 indicates that the effect of Job Satisfaction on Worklife Balance is positive.

2. *Hypothesis 2*

Ho1 : Job Stress has no positive effect on Work Life Balance

Ha1 : Job Stress has a negative effect on Work Life Balance

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, the p-value is $0.006 \leq 0.05$ (error rate $\alpha = 5\%$) so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that Job Stress has a negative effect on Worklife Balance. This means that if Job Stress increases, Worklife Balance will decrease and vice versa, if Job Stress decreases, Worklife Balance will increase. The estimate value of -0.189 shows that the effect of Job Stress on Worklife Balance is negative

3. Hypothesis 3

H_{01} : Worklife Balance does not have a positive effect on Organizational Commitment

H_{a1} : Worklife Balance has a positive effect on organizational commitment

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, the p-value is $0.028 \leq 0.05$ (error rate $\alpha = 5\%$) so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that Worklife Balance has a positive effect on Organizational commitment. This means that if Worklife Balance increases, Organizational commitment will increase and vice versa, if Worklife Balance decreases, Organizational commitment will decrease. The estimate value of 0.148 indicates that the effect of Worklife Balance on Organizational commitment is positive.

4. Hypothesis 4

H_{01} : Job satisfaction does not have a positive effect on organizational commitment

H_{a1} : Job satisfaction has a positive effect on organizational commitment

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the p-value is $0.000 \leq 0.05$ (error rate $\alpha = 5\%$) so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that Job Satisfaction has a positive effect on Organizational commitment. This means that if Job Satisfaction increases, Organizational commitment will increase and vice versa, if Job Satisfaction decreases, Organizational commitment will decrease. The estimate value of 0.606 indicates that the effect of Job Satisfaction on Organizational commitment is positive.

5. Hypothesis 5

H_{01} : Work stress has no effect on organizational commitment

H_{a1} : Work stress has a negative effect on organizational commitment

Based on the results of the hypothesis testing, the p-value is $0.561 \leq 0.05$ (error rate $\alpha = 5\%$) so H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected. This means that Job Stress has no effect on Organizational commitment. This means that there is no significant relationship between job stress and Organizational commitment.

CONCLUSION

This study confirms that the hypotheses H1, H2, H3, and H4 proposed in this study are proven. First, job satisfaction has a significant effect on work-life balance. Second, job stress has a significant effect on work-life balance. Third, work-life balance has a significant effect on organizational commitment. Fourth, job satisfaction has an effect on organizational commitment moderated by work-life balance. While hypothesis H5 is not proven in this study. The fifth hypothesis is that job stress has an effect on organizational commitment moderated by work-life balance.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the conclusions of the research results, the suggestions that can be given from the research analysis are as follows:

1. Further research is expected to be conducted in a wider area, so that it can capture more diverse responses and characteristics of respondents.
2. Further research is expected to add other variables that influence organizational commitment.
3. Further research is expected to use other research objects with different types of industries.

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